

Synthesis of Aza-S(VI) Fluorides and Primary Sulfonimidamides from Sulfinylamines

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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1. General experimental conditions

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Fluorochem, TCI Europe, and BLDpharm, and used as supplied. For thin layer chromatography (TLC) aluminium sheets precoated with silica gel 60F₂₅₄ (Merck) were used. Visualization of the spots was performed using UV light ($\lambda = 254$ nm), or KMnO₄ (aq.) and heat. Solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. Flash column chromatography was performed using silica gel (Merck Kieselgel Gerduran - 0.040-0.063 mm). NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Ascend-400 (400 MHz for ¹H-NMR, 101 MHz for ¹³C{¹H}-NMR and 377 MHz for ¹⁹F-NMR) at ambient temperature. Peaks of the residual non-deuterated solvents were used as the reference in relation to TMS with δ 7.26 ppm (¹H in CDCl₃), δ 77.00 ppm (¹³C in CDCl₃) or 49.00 ppm (¹³C in CD₃OD). Absolute referencing was used for ¹⁹F spectra. NMR data is reported as following: s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), sept (septet), m (multiplet) and combinations thereof. Spin-spin coupling constants (*J*) are reported in Hertz. High resolution mass analysis was performed on Agilent 6530 accurate mass Q-TOF instrument and Excalibur data system (operating in positive and negative modes). Thermo Scientific Nicolet Summit PRO FTIR Spectrometer was employed to obtain the infrared spectra recorded in cm⁻¹ and samples were loaded neat. THF was freshly distilled from benzophenone ketyl/sodium and diethyl ether was freshly distilled from CaH₂ before use. Organometallic solutions were titrated before use according to standard procedures.^{1,2}

2. Synthesis of substrates

2.1 Synthesis of sulfinylamines

N-sulfinyltritylamine was synthesized according to the reported procedure.³ N-sulfinylcumylamine and N-sulfinylanilines were prepared following the same procedure from the corresponding amines.

To a solution of amine (2 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry diethyl ether (0.56 M), triethylamine (4 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) was added, and the solution was cooled to 0 °C before adding thionyl chloride dropwise (2 mmol, 1.0 equiv.). The solution was stirred at 0 °C for two hours. The solution was filtered through a celite-pad and washed with dry diethyl ether (3 x 15 mL). The organic solution was concentrated under reduced pressure to afford the corresponding N-sulfinylamine without further purification.

NB: Sulfinylamines **1c,d** rapidly hydrolysed non anhydrous CDCl₃.

2.2 Synthesis of aryllithiums from aryl halides

To a solution of aryl halide (Br, I) in dry THF (1.0 M) under nitrogen atmosphere cooled to -78 °C, n-BuLi (2.5 M in hexane, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the solution was stirred at -78 °C for 5 minutes. The solution of aryllithium was subsequently used without further purifications.

NB. The use of 4-lithioisoquinoline proved unsuccessful when used following **GP1**. Similarly, the addition of n-BuLi to a mixture of 4-bromoisoquinoline and TrNSO, hence generating the organolithium in Barbier-type conditions, proved unsuccessful in releasing the corresponding sulfonimidoyl fluoride.

2.3 Synthesis of 2-benzofuranylithium

To a solution of benzofuran in dry THF (1.0 M) under nitrogen atmosphere cooled to 0 °C, *n*-BuLi (2.5 M in hexane, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the solution was stirred at room temperature for 3 hours. The solution of 2-benzofuranylithium was subsequently used without further purifications.

3. General procedure 1 (GP1)- Synthesis of *N*-trityl sulfonimidoyl fluorides

To a solution of *N*-sulfinyltritylamine (50 mg, 0.16 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry THF (0.25 M) under nitrogen atmosphere, organometallic solution (0.16 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 minute. Subsequently, NFSI (0.18 mmol, 57 mg, 1.1 equiv.) was added in one portion and the reaction was stirred for additional 5 minutes (complete conversion was checked by TLC plate analysis). The solution was directly concentrated under reduced pressure, and the crude was purified by column chromatography as indicated for each entry to afford the desired sulfonimidoyl fluoride.

Preparation of **2a** -1.0 mmol scale.

To a solution of *N*-sulfinyltritylamine (305 mg, 1.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry THF (0.25 M) under nitrogen atmosphere, phenyllithium solution (1.9 M in dibutyl ether, 1.0 mmol, 526 μ L, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 minute. Subsequently, NFSI (1.10 mmol, 347 mg, 1.1 equiv.) was added in one portion and the reaction was stirred for additional 5 minutes. The solution was directly concentrated under reduced pressure, and the crude was purified by column chromatography (Hex:AcOEt 9:1) to afford sulfonimidoyl fluoride **2a** as a white solid (357 mg, 89%).

Characterization data for compound **2a-o**

N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (**2a**)

Compound **2a** was prepared following **GP1** using phenyllithium (1.9 M in dibutyl ether) and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 58mg, 90%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.18 – 8.17 (m, 2H), 7.70 – 7.69 (m, 1H), 7.62 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.52 – 7.50 (m, 6H), 7.38 – 7.21 (m overlapping CDCl_3 , 9H). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 91.06. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.4 (d, $J = 4.3$ Hz), 138.4 (d, $J = 29.3$ Hz), 133.7, 129.3, 128.9, 127.9, 127.5, 127.2, 74.2 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz). Spectroscopic data in agreement with literature.⁴

N-tritylethenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (**2b**)

Compound **2b** was prepared following **GP1** using vinylmagnesium bromide (1.0 M in THF) and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 54 mg, 96%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.44 – 7.41 (m, 6H), 7.38 – 7.24 (m, 9H), 6.84 (ddd, $J = 16.5, 9.7, 2.4$ Hz, 1H), 6.53 (d, $J = 16.5$ Hz, 1H), 6.14 (dd, $J = 9.4, 4.5$ Hz, 1H). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 85.39 (dd, $J = 4.4, 2.2$ Hz). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.2 (d, $J = 4.5$ Hz), 134.8 (d, $J = 33.6$ Hz), 128.8, 128.4, 127.9, 127.2, 74.0 (d, $J = 4.7$ Hz). IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3057, 2923, 1446, 1362, 1208, 748, 698. HRMS (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$ calcd for $[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{FNNaOS}]^+$ 374.0991; found 374.0996.

N-tritylprop-1-ene-2-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2c)

Compound **2c** was prepared following **GP1** using *iso*-propenylmagnesium bromide (0.5 M in THF) and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 29 mg, 50%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.43 – 7.39 (m, 6H), 7.33 – 7.24 (m, 9H), 6.29 (s, 1H), 5.79 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.38 (s, 3H). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 75.49 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.4 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz), 128.9, 128.1 (d, $J = 1.2$ Hz), 127.9, 127.1, 124.2, 73.9, 18.1. IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3057, 2924, 1446, 1352, 1178, 757, 698. HRMS (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$ calcd for $[\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{FNNaOS}]^+$ 388.1147; found 388.1142.

N-tritylpropane-2-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2d)

Compound **2d** was prepared following **GP1** using *iso*-propylmagnesium chloride lithium chloride complex (1.3 M in THF) and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 48mg, 82%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.42 (d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 6H), 7.33 – 7.24 (m, 9H), 3.69 – 3.60 (m, 1H), 1.64 – 1.60 (m, 6H). ^{19}F

NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 63.56. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.6 (d, *J* = 4.5 Hz), 128.9, 127.8, 127.0, 73.2 (d, *J* = 5.1 Hz), 57.5 (d, *J* = 20.0 Hz), 18.0, 17.6. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3057, 1446, 1345, 1200, 897, 696, 628. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₂H₂₂FNNaOS]⁺ 390.1304; found 390.1329.

N-tritylbutane-1-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2e)

Compound **2e** was prepared following **GP1** using *n*BuLi (2.5 M in hexane) and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 55 mg, 90%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.43 – 7.39 (m, 6H), 7.33 – 7.24 (m, 9H), 3.46 – 3.44 (m, 2H), 2.09 – 2.01 (m, 2H), 1.58 – 1.56 (m, 2H), 1.03 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 77.25. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.4 (d, *J* = 4.4 Hz), 128.8, 127.7, 127.1, 73.6 (d, *J* = 4.8 Hz), 55.2 (d, *J* = 21.7 Hz), 26.3, 21.3, 13.6. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2959, 1447, 1351, 1193, 899, 773, 697. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₃H₂₄FNNaOS]⁺ 404.1460; found 404.1457.

2-phenyl-N-tritylethane-1-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2f)

Compound **2f** was prepared following **GP1** using phenethylmagnesium bromide (1.0 M in THF) and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 28 mg, 41%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.43 – 7.41 (m, 6H), 7.37 – 7.24 (m, 14H), 3.76 – 3.68 (m, 2H), 3.35 – 3.32 (m, 2H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 76.69. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.3 (d, *J* = 4.4 Hz), 137.0, 129.1, 128.8, 128.6, 127.9, 127.4, 127.2, 73.8 (d, *J* = 4.9 Hz), 56.8 (d, *J* = 21.8), 30.7. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3058, 2926, 1701, 1362, 1197, 746, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₇H₂₄FNNaSO]⁺ 452.1460; found 452.1459.

4-methyl-N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2g)

Compound **2g** was prepared following **GP1** using (4-methylphenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 48 mg, 73%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.03 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.50 – 7.45 (m, 6H), 7.38 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.35 – 7.24 (m overlapping CDCl₃ 9H), 2.47 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 91.10. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.4 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz), 144.8, 135.4 (d, *J* = 28.7 Hz), 129.9, 128.9, 127.8, 127.3, 127.0, 73.9 (d, *J* = 4.8 Hz), 21.6. Spectroscopic data in agreement with literature.⁴

4-fluoro-N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2h)

Compound **2h** was prepared following **GP1** using (4-fluorophenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 49 mg, 72%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.21 – 8.15 (m, 2H), 7.48 – 7.45 (m, 6H), 7.38 – 7.25 (m overlapping CDCl₃ 11H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 92.09, -103.39 (tt, *J* = 8.4, 5.0 Hz). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 165.8 (d, *J* = 256.7 Hz), 146.2 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 134.2 (d, *J* = 30.6 Hz), 130.4 (d, *J* = 9.6 Hz), 128.9, 128.0, 127.3, 116.6 (d, *J* = 22.9 Hz), 74.3 (d, *J* = 4.8 Hz) **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2921, 2852, 1365, 1213, 1153, 754, 630. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₅H₁₉F₂NNaOS]⁺ 442.1053; found 442.1074.

4-methoxy-N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2i)

Compound **2i** was prepared following **GP1** using (4-methoxyphenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 49 mg, 70%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.07 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 2H), 7.47 – 7.44 (m, 6H), 7.35

– 7.24 (m overlapping CDCl₃, 9H), 7.03 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 2H), 3.90 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 91.72. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 163.9, 146.5 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 129.8, 128.9, 127.9, 127.1, 114.5, 74.0, 55.9. Spectroscopic data in agreement with literature.⁴

4-vinyl-N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2j)

Compound **2j** was prepared following **GP1** using (4-vinylphenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 56 mg, 82%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.12 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.62 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.53 – 7.47 (m, 6H), 7.39 – 7.27 (m overlapping CDCl₃, 9H), 6.82 (dd, *J* = 17.6, 10.9 Hz, 1H), 5.95 (d, *J* = 17.6 Hz, 1H), 5.51 (d, *J* = 10.9 Hz, 1H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 91.46. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.4 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 143.0, 137.0 (d, *J* = 29.5 Hz), 135.3, 128.9, 127.9, 127.9, 127.2, 126.9, 118.2, 74.2 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3057, 2923, 1446, 1356, 1213, 755, 695. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₇H₂₂FNNaOS]⁺ 450.1304; found 450.1338.

4-(methylthio)-N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2k)

Compound **2k** was prepared following **GP1** using (4-(methylthio)phenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 30 mg, 42%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.04 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.48 – 7.47 (m, 6H), 7.39 – 7.27 (m, overlapping CDCl₃ 11H), 2.57 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 91.72. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 147.3, 146.3 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 133.9 (d, *J* = 29.8 Hz), 128.8, 127.9, 127.8, 127.0, 125.3, 74.0 (d, *J* = 4.7 Hz), 14.8. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2922, 2852, 1446, 1359, 1213, 757, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₆H₂₂FNNaOS₂]⁺ 470.1025; found 470.1037.

2-vinyl-N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2l)

Compound **2l** was prepared following **GP1** using (2-vinylphenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 30 mg, 44%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.17 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 1.0 Hz, 1H) 7.72 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz 1H), 7.65 – 7.48 (m, 2H), 7.47 – 7.39 (m, 7H), 7.34 – 7.20 (m overlapping CDCl₃, 9H), 5.78 (d, *J* = 17.3 Hz, 1H), 5.44 (d, *J* = 11.0, 1H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 88.58. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.4 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz), 137.5, 136.2 (d, *J* = 28.5 Hz), 133.8, 133.6, 129.0, 128.6, 128.2, 128.1, 127.9, 127.8, 118.8, 74.9 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3058, 2923, 1446, 1349, 1210, 765, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₇H₂₂FNNaOS]⁺ 450.1304; found 450.1304.

N-tritylnaphthalene-1-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2m)

Compound **2m** was prepared following **GP1** using (2-naphthyl)lithium and was obtained as a pink powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 53 mg, 74%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.82 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 8.49 – 8.46 (m, 1H), 8.17 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 8.03 – 7.97 (m, 1H), 7.78 – 7.57 (m, 3H), 7.56 – 7.50 (m, 6H), 7.41 – 7.23 (m overlapping CDCl₃, 9H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 88.24. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.5 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 135.1, 134.5 (d, *J* = 29.7 Hz), 134.5, 129.0, 128.9, 128.6, 128.5, 127.9, 127.3, 127.2, 125.7, 125.7, 124.1, 74.9 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3057, 2922, 1447, 1346, 1210, 767, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₉H₂₂FNNaOS]⁺ 474.1304; found 474.1315

N-tritylthiophene-2-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2n)

Compound **2n** was prepared following **GP1** using 2-thienylmagnesium chloride lithium chloride complex and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 62 mg, 95%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.80 – 7.78 (m, 1H), 7.72 (dd, *J* = 5.1, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.53 – 7.45 (m, 6H), 7.37 – 7.26 (m overlapping CDCl₃, 9H), 7.17–7.15 (m, 1H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 97.15. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.2 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz), 138.4 (d, *J* = 35.7 Hz), 133.9, 133.4, 128.8, 128.0, 127.8, 127.2, 74.5 (d, *J* = 4.4 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2924, 2853, 1489, 1264, 1217, 734, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₃H₁₈FNNaS₂O]⁺ 430.0712; found 430.0705.

N-tritylbenzofuran-2-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2o)

Compound **2o** was prepared following **GP1** using 2-benzofuranyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 42 mg, 60%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.76 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.67 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 7.61 – 7.54 (m, 2H), 7.53 – 7.48 (m, 6H), 7.44 – 7.28 (m, 10H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 91.00. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.1, 147.2 (d, *J* = 44.1 Hz), 146.0 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 128.8, 128.6, 128.1, 127.4, 125.8, 124.7, 123.3, 114.0, 112.8, 74.9 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2923, 2853, 1490, 1445, 1378, 1177, 749, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₇H₂₀FNNaO₂S]⁺ 464.1096; found 464.1081

4. General procedure 2 (GP2)- Synthesis of *N*-cumyl sulfonimidoyl fluorides

To a cooled solution of *N*-sulfinylcumylamine (100 mg, 0.55 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry THF (0.25 M) at 0 °C, under nitrogen atmosphere, organometallic solution (0.55 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 15 minutes. Subsequently, NFSI (0.6 mmol, 191 mg, 1.1 equiv.) was added in one portion and the reaction was stirred for additional 5 minutes at room temperature (complete conversion was checked by TLC plate analysis). The solution was then directly concentrated under reduced pressure, and the crude product was purified by column chromatography as indicated for each entry to afford the desired sulfonimidoyl fluoride.

Characterization data for compound **2p-v**

N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)benzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2p)

Compound **2o** was prepared following **GP2** using phenyllithium (1.9 M in dibutyl ether) and was obtained as a sticky solid after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 91 mg, 60%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.11 – 8.09 (m, 2H), 7.70 – 7.65 (m, 1H), 7.61 – 7.56 (m, 4H), 7.40 – 7.36 (m, 2H), 7.29 – 7.23 (m, overlapping CDCl₃ 1H), 1.89 (s, 3H), 1.88 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 92.27. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.7 (d, *J* = 4.0 Hz), 137.8 (d, *J* = 28.2 Hz), 133.7, 129.2, 128.3, 127.7, 126.7, 125.1, 61.9 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz), 32.9 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz), 32.7 (d, *J* = 5.2 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2977, 2926, 1447, 1354, 1210, 733, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (*M*+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₅H₁₆FNNaOS]⁺ 300.0834; found 300.0834.

N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)thiophene-2-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2q)

Compound **2q** was prepared following **GP2** using 2-thienylmagnesium chloride lithium chloride complex and was obtained as a sticky solid after column chromatography on silica

gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 104 mg, 67%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.83-7.81 (m, 1H), 7.69 (dd, J = 5.1, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.60 – 7.57 (m, 2H), 7.41 – 7.34 (m, 2H), 7.30 – 7.25 (m, overlapping CDCl₃ 1H), 7.16-7.15 (m, 1 H) 1.88 (s, 6H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 98.56. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.5 (d, J = 4.1 Hz), 137.9 (d, J = 34.7 Hz), 134.0, 133.5, 128.3, 127.7, 126.7, 125.0, 62.5 (d, J = 4.3 Hz), 32.9 (d, J = 2.0 Hz), 32.8 (d, J = 4.8 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2979, 2853, 1402, 1342, 1208, 1022, 763, 697. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₃H₁₄FNNaOS₂]⁺ 306.0399; found 306.0401.

4-fluoro-N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)benzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2r)

Compound **2r** was prepared following **GP2** using (4-fluorophenyl)lithium and was obtained as a yellow oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 121 mg, 75%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.16 – 8.13 (m, 2H), 7.60-7.56 (m, 2H), 7.39 (t, J = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 7.30 – 7.24 (m, 3H), 1.91 (s, 3H), 1.90 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 93.21, -103.55 – -103.62 (m). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 165.9 (d, J = 256.4 Hz), 148.6 (d, J = 4.1 Hz), 133.8 (d, J = 32.5 Hz), 130.6 (d, J = 9.6 Hz), 128.3, 126.8, 125.0, 116.5 (d, J = 22.9 Hz), 62.0 (d, J = 4.5 Hz), 32.9 (d, J = 2.1 Hz), 32.6 (d, J = 4.9 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2979, 1590, 1493, 1354, 1207, 1153, 837, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₆H₁₉F₂NNaOS]⁺ 318.0740; found 318.0744.

N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)hexane-1-sulfonimidoyl fluoride (2s)

Compound **2s** was prepared following **GP2** using hexyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 80 mg, 49%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.54 – 7.51 (m, 2H), 7.39 – 7.32 (m, 2H), 7.29 – 7.22 (m, 1H), 3.45 – 3.30 (m, 2H), 2.04 – 1.95 (m, 2H), 1.79 (s, 3H), 1.78 (s, 3H) 1.52 – 1.45 (m, 2H), 1.38 – 1.33 (m, 4H), 0.95 – 0.89 (m, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 79.52. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.9, 128.2, 126.6, 125.0, 61.3 (d, J = 4.7 Hz), 54.8 (d, J = 20.8 Hz), 32.7 (d, J = 2.2 Hz), 32.3 (d, J = 5.5 Hz), 27.6, 24.4, 22.5, 14.1. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2920, 2857, 1446,

1345, 1202, 762, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₅H₂₄FNNaOS]⁺ 308.1460; found 308.1456.

4-methoxy-N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)benzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2t)

Compound **2t** was prepared following **GP2** using (4-methoxyphenyl)lithium and was obtained as a yellow oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 125 mg, 74%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.03 – 8.01 (m, 2H), 7.58 – 7.56 (m, 2H), 7.38 (t, J = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 7.29 – 7.24 (m, 1H), 7.05 – 6.99 (m, 2H), 3.89 (s, 3H), 1.87 (s, 3H), 1.86 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 92.73. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 163.8, 149.0 (d, J = 4.0 Hz), 130.0, 129.4 (d, J = 28.1 Hz), 128.3, 126.6, 125.1, 114.3, 61.7 (d, J = 4.5 Hz), 55.9, 32.9 (d, J = 1.9 Hz), 32.7 (d, J = 5.0 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2977, 2852, 1594, 1496, 1208, 1170, 763. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₆H₁₈FNNaO₂S]⁺ 330.0940; found 330.0924.

N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)-4-vinylbenzenesulfonimidoyl fluoride (2u)

Compound **2u** was prepared following **GP2** using (4-vinylphenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 115 mg, 69%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.05 – 8.04 (m, 2H), 7.56 – 7.54 (m, 3H), 7.37 – 7.35 (m, 2H), 7.30 – 7.24 (m, 2H), 6.79 (dd, J = 17.6, 10.9 Hz, 1H), 5.91 (d, J = 17.6 Hz, 1H), 5.47 (d, J = 10.9 Hz, 1H), 1.89 (s, 3H), 1.87 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 92.64. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.8, 142.9, 136.5 (d, J = 28.5 Hz), 135.4, 128.3, 128.1, 126.7, 126.7, 125.1, 118.1, 61.9 (d, J = 4.4 Hz), 32.9 (d, J = 2.0 Hz), 32.7 (d, J = 5.1 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2924, 1352, 1210, 1180, 763, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₇H₁₈FNNaOS]⁺ 326.0991; found 326.0979.

N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)-2-benzofuranylsulfonimidoyl fluoride (2v)

Compound **2v** was prepared following **GP2** using 2-benzofuranyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 105 mg, 60%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.73 – 7.72 (m, 1H), 7.67 – 7.52 (m, 5H), 7.43 – 7.37 (m, 3H), 7.33 – 7.28 (m, 1H), 1.91 (s, 3H), 1.89 (s, 3H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 92.70. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.0, 148.1 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 147.0 (d, *J* = 42.4 Hz), 128.5, 128.4, 126.9, 125.8, 125.0, 124.6, 123.3, 114.1 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz), 112.8, 62.9 (d, *J* = 4.4 Hz), 33.2 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz), 33.0 (d, *J* = 4.9 Hz). **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2924, 2853, 1444, 1209, 749, 656. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₇H₁₆FNNaO₂S]⁺ 340.0778; found 340.0779.

5. General procedure 3 (GP3)- Synthesis of *N*-aryl sulfonylimidoyl fluorides

To a cooled solution of *N*-sulfinylarylamine (1.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry THF (0.25 M) at -78 °C, under nitrogen atmosphere, organometallic solution (1.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 15 minutes. Subsequently, NFSI (1.1 mmol, 347 mg, 1.1 equiv.) was added in one portion and the reaction was stirred for additional 15 minutes at room temperature. The solution was directly concentrated under reduced pressure, and the crude product was purified by column chromatography as indicated for each entry to afford the desired sulfonylimidoyl fluoride.

Characterization data for compound **2w,x**

N-(2,6-dimethylphenyl)butane-1-sulfonylimidoyl fluoride (2w)

Compound **2w** was prepared following **GP3** using *n*-butyllithium and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 95:05, 51 mg, 21%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.03 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 6.97 – 6.94 (m, 1H), 3.66 – 3.48 (m, 2H), 2.31 (s, 6H), 2.15 – 2.07 (m, 2H), 1.66 – 1.52 (m, 2H), 1.03 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H). ¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 80.55. ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 136.8 (d, *J* = 5.7 Hz), 132.8 (d, *J* = 6.0 Hz), 128.2, 124.7, 53.5 (d, *J* = 20.9 Hz), 26.3, 21.5, 19.2, 19.2, 13.6. IR (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2923, 2853, 1348, 1261, 766, 665. HRMS (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₂H₁₈FNNaOS]⁺ 266.0985; found 266.0984.

N-(4-trifluoromethylphenyl)butane-1-sulfonylimidoyl fluoride (2x)

Compound **2x** was prepared following **GP3** using *n*-butyllithium and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 95:05, 51 mg, 18%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 3.59 – 3.42 (m, 2H), 2.09 – 2.00 (m, 2H), 1.52 – 1.42 (m, 2H), 1.02 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H). ¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 69.56 (s, 1F), -62.11 (s, 3F). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 143.3 (d, *J* = 6.0 Hz), 126.6 (q, *J* = 3.5 Hz), 124.4 (q, *J* = 271.4 Hz), 126.1, 124.0 (d, *J* = 4.7 Hz), 53.4 (d,

$J = 17.7$ Hz), 25.8, 21.3, 13.5. **IR** (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 2926, 1516, 1320, 1059, 843, 733. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for $[\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{F}_4\text{NNaOS}]^+$ 306.0546; found 306.0543.

6. General procedure 4 (GP4)- Synthesis of sulfonimidamides

To a solution of *N*-sulfinylamine (0.33 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry THF (0.25 M) under nitrogen atmosphere, LiHMDS (1.0 M in THF, 1.0 equiv., 330 μ L) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 5 minutes at room temperature. Subsequently, the solution was cooled to 0 °C and the organometallic solution (0.33 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 1 minute. NFSI (0.36 mmol, 114 mg, 1.1 equiv.) was added in one portion and the reaction was stirred for additional 15 minutes at 0 °C, before adding NaOH (2.0 equiv., 26 mg) and water (250 μ L). The solution was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into water (15 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (3 x 15 mL). The combined organic layers were collected, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtered, and the solvent was evaporated at reduced pressure. The compounds were purified by column chromatography as indicated for each entry to afford the desired sulfonimidamide.

Characterization data for compound **5a-o**

N'-tritylsulfonimidamide (**5a**)

Compound **5a** was prepared following **GP4** using phenyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 95 mg, 72%) $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.99 (d, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), δ 7.62 (d, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 6H) 7.54 – 7.43 (m, 3H), 7.32 – 7.23 (m, 9H), 4.00 (broad signal, 2H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.1, 145.5, 131.4, 129.0, 128.7, 127.8, 126.7, 126.3, 72.3. IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3247, 3056, 1445, 1278, 1167, 750, 700. HRMS (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$ calcd for $[\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{NaOS}]^+$ 421.1351; found 421.1381.

N'-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)sulfonimidamide (**5b**)

Compound **5b** was prepared following **GP4** using phenyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 5:5, 46 mg, 50%) $^1\text{H NMR}$

(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.90 – 7.82 (m, 2H), 7.49 – 7.44 (m, 1H), 7.39 (td, *J* = 6.0, 2.6 Hz, 4H), 7.26 – 7.16 (m, 3H), 4.08 (broad signal, 2H), 1.63 (s, 3H), 1.62 (s, 3H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.4, 144.4, 131.6, 128.7, 128.3, 127.0, 126.9, 125.6, 58.7, 30.1, 29.4. IR (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3252, 3060, 2976, 2925, 1444, 1239, 751. HRMS (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₅H₁₈N₂NaOS]⁺ 297.1032; found 297.1032.

N'-tritylpropane-2-sulfonimidamide (5c)

Compound **5c** was prepared following **GP4** using isopropylmagnesium chloride lithium chloride complex and was obtained as a sticky solid after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 59 mg, 49%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.56 – 7.54 (m, 6H), 7.30 – 7.26 (m, 6H), 7.22 – 7.19 (m, 3H), 3.25 – 3.23 (m, 1H), 3.05 (s, 1H), 1.53 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H), 1.49 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.0, 129.0, 127.9, 126.6, 71.4, 59.2, 17.5, 17.5. IR (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3414, 3241, 3056, 2925, 1278, 755, 701. HRMS (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₂H₂₄N₂NaOS]⁺ 387.1507; found 387.1514.

N'-tritylbutane-1-sulfonimidamide (5d)

Compound **5d** was prepared following **GP4** using n-butyllithium and was obtained as a waxy solid after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 69 mg, 55%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.61 – 7.58 (m, 6H), 7.34 – 7.27 (m, 6H), 7.27 – 7.21 (m, 3H), 3.04 (broad signal, 4H), 2.10 – 1.84 (m, 2H), 1.56 – 1.34 (m, 2H), 0.99 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 147.3, 128.9, 127.9, 126.8, 71.8, 59.1, 26.4, 21.5, 13.9. IR (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3241, 3056, 2923, 1446, 1266, 745, 701. HRMS (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₃H₂₆N₂NaOS]⁺ 377.1688; found 377.1696.

N'-tritylhexane-1-sulfonimidamide (5e)

Compound **5e** was prepared following **GP4** using hexyllithium and was obtained as a waxy solid after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 79 mg, 57%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.61 – 7.58 (m, 6H), 7.34 – 7.22 (m, 9H), 3.27 – 3.04 (broad signal, 4H), 1.99 – 1.91 (m, 2H), 1.46 – 1.29 (m, 8H), 0.94 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.3, 129.0, 127.9, 126.8, 71.8, 59.4, 31.5, 28.0, 24.4, 22.6, 14.4. IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3238, 3056, 2924, 2855, 1488, 1274, 700. HRMS (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$ calcd for $[\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{NaOS}]^+$ 429.1971; found 429.1962.

N'-tritylthiophene-2-sulfonimidamide (5f)

Compound **5f** was prepared following **GP4** using 2-thienylmagnesium chloride lithium chloride complex and was obtained as a waxy solid after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 73 mg, 55%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.60 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 6H), 7.47– 7.42, (m, 2H), 7.35 – 7.26 (m, overlapping CDCl_3 6H), 7.26 – 7.18 (m, 3H), 7.00 – 6.97 (m, 1H), 3.78 (s, 2H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.9, 130.6, 129.9, 129.4, 128.9, 127.7, 127.1, 126.6, 72.5. IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3399, 3240, 3057, 1446, 1293, 1172, 745, 698. HRMS (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{H}$) $^+$ calcd for $[\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{OS}_2]^+$ 403.0939; found 403.0946.

N'-tritylnaphthalene-1-sulfonimidamide (5g)

Compound **5g** was prepared following **GP4** using 2-naphthyllithium and was obtained as a pink powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 83 mg, 56%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.88 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.08 – 8.05 (m, 1H), 7.98 – 7.92 (m, 2H), 7.65 – 7.49 (m, 8H), 7.43 – 7.25 (m overlapping CDCl_3 , 6H), 7.25 – 7.17 (m, 4H), 3.66 (broad signal, 2H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) 148.7, 146.8, 134.4, 133.0, 129.9, 129.1, 128.3, 128.0, 127.7, 126.7, 126.7, 126.4, 125.4, 124.3, 73.0 IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3240, 3055, 2924,

1445, 1264, 1164, 734, 696. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+H)⁺ calcd for [C₂₉H₂₃N₂OS]⁻ 447.1531; found 447.1533.

4-fluoro-N'-tritylsulfonimidamide (5h)

Compound **5h** was prepared following **GP4** using 4-fluorophenyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 87 mg, 63%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.91– 7.89 (m, 2H), 7.58 – 7.52 (m, 6H), 7.31 – 7.21 (m overlapping CDCl₃, 9H), 7.11 – 7.04 (m, 3H), 3.79 (broad signal, 2H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -107.95. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 164.5 (d, $J = 252.8$ Hz), 146.7, 129.2 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz), 129.0, 128.2 (d, $J = 21.1$ Hz), 127.9, 126.9, 115.7 (d, $J = 22.5$ Hz), 72.5. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3246, 3057, 2923, 1490, 1151, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₅H₂₁N₂NaOS]⁺ 439.1251; found 439.1252.

4-methoxy-N'-tritylsulfonimidamide (5i)

Compound **5i** was prepared following **GP4** using 4-methoxyphenyllithium and was obtained as a pale pink powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 83 mg, 59%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.88 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.58 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 6H), 7.37 – 7.14 (m, 9H), 6.91 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 2H), 3.88 (s, 5H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 162.1, 147.0, 137.3, 129.1, 128.5, 127.8, 126.7, 113.8, 72.3, 55.7. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3066, 2924, 2853, 1594, 1494, 1254, 1103, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₆H₂₄N₂NaO₂S]⁺ 451.1451; found 451.1447.

4-vinyl-N'-tritylsulfonimidamide (5j)

Compound **5j** was prepared following **GP4** using 4-vinylphenyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 84 mg, 60%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.89 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.63 – 7.51 (m, 6H), 7.43 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.31 – 7.17 (m, 11H), 6.74 (dd, *J* = 17.6, 10.9 Hz, 1H), 5.85 (d, *J* = 17.6 Hz, 1H), 5.39 (d, *J* = 10.9 Hz, 1H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 147.0, 140.8, 135.8, 129.1, 128.3, 128.1, 127.9, 126.8, 126.5, 116.7, 72.5. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3056, 2922, 2852, 1445, 1275, 840. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₇H₂₄N₂NaOS]⁺ 447.1502; found 447.1494.

4-fluoro-2,6-dimethyl-N'-tritylsulfonimidamide (5k)

Compound **5k** was prepared following **GP4** using 4-fluoro-2,6-dimethylphenyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 73 mg, 50%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.53 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 6H), 7.27 – 7.20 (m, 9H), 6.74 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 2H), 3.90 (broad signal, 2H), 2.60 (s, 6H). **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -111.34 (t, *J* = 9.3 Hz). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 162.5 (d, *J* = 251.0 Hz), 146.4, 140.8 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz), 128.9, 127.8, 126.8, 117.4 (d, *J* = 21.2 Hz), 73.0, 23.2. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3244, 2922, 2853, 1445, 1287, 729. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₇H₂₅FN₂NaOS]⁺ 467.1564; found 467.1560.

4-(methylthio)-N'-tritylsulfonimidamide (5l)

Compound **5l** was prepared following **GP4** using 4-(methylthio)phenyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 61 mg, 42%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.85 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.60 – 7.58 (m, 6H), 7.31 – 7.21 (m, 11H), 2.54 (s, 3H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 147.0, 143.8, 141.6, 129.0, 127.8, 126.8, 126.7, 125.4, 72.4, 15.2. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3244, 2922, 1445, 1081, 729, 698. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₆H₂₄N₂NaOS]⁺ 467.1222; found 467.1219.

3-chloro-N'-tritylsulfonimidamide (5m)

Compound **5m** was prepared following **GP4** using 3-chlorophenyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 74 mg, 52%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.77 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.55 – 7.49 (m, 6H), 7.44 – 7.39 (m, 1H), 7.32 (t, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.29 – 7.17 (m overlapping CDCl₃, 9H), 4.00 (broad signal, 2H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.7, 146.5, 134.7, 131.6, 129.9, 129.1, 127.9, 127.0, 126.9, 124.6, 72.6. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3248, 3058, 2924, 1278, 907, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₅H₂₁ClN₂NaOS]⁺ 455.0955; found 455.0957.

N'-tritylbenzofuran-2-sulfonimidamide (5n)

Compound **5n** was prepared following **GP4** using 2-benzofuranyllithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 74 mg, 51%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.55 – 7.48 (m, 7H), 7.45 – 7.26 (m, 7H overlapping CDCl₃), 7.24 – 7.14 (m, 6H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.5, 149.0, 129.8, 129.3, 128.6, 128.4, 128.2, 127.3, 127.2, 124.3, 122.9, 112.5, 73.1. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3248, 3058, 2924, 1446, 1278, 907, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₇H₂₂N₂NaO₂S]⁺ 461.1294; found 461.1304.

4-(5-(*p*-tolyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-N'-tritylbenzenesulfonimidamide (5o)

Compound **5o** was prepared following **GP4** using (4-(5-(*p*-tolyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)phenyl)lithium and was obtained as a white powder after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 7:3, 103 mg, 50%) **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

7.92 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.57 – 7.51 (m, 6H), 7.38 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.32 – 7.25 (m, 7H), 7.24 – 7.19 (m, 4H), 7.17 – 7.14 (m, 2H), 6.75 (s, 1H), 3.80 (broad signal, 2H), 2.40 (s, 3H). **^{19}F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.40 (s). **$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 148.8, 146.9, 145.3, 145.0, 144.1 (q, $J = 38.4$ Hz), 142.0, 139.8, 129.9, 129.0, 128.3, 128.8, 127.6, 126.9, 126.1, 125.1, 121.3 (q, $J = 269.0$ Hz), 72.7, 21.5. **IR** (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3244, 3057, 2923, 1595, 1236, 702. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$ [$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{29}\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{NaOS}$] $^+$ 645.1906; found 645.1903.

7. Preparation of sulfonimidamide salt **6**

Sulfonimidamide **5o** (0.16 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was treated with HCl (3.0 M in EtOAc, 0.107 mL, 2.0 equiv.) at 20 °C for 18 h. The white precipitate was washed with EtOAc (3 x 15 mL) and dried under vacuum to furnish compound **6** as a white solid without further purifications.⁵

4-(5-(*p*-tolyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)benzenesulfonimidamide hydrochloride (**6**)

Compound **6** was obtained following the deprotection procedure as a white powder (95%, 63 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.19 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.73 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.28 – 7.19 (m, 4H), 6.96 (s, 1H), 2.38 (s, 3H). ¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CD₃OD) δ -64.01 (s). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 146.0, 144.5, 144.06 (q, *J* = 38.5 Hz), 139.9, 136.7, 129.4, 128.8, 128.7, 126.2, 125.6, 125.1, 122.5, 119.8, 117.1, 106.1, 19.9. IR (ATR, cm⁻¹) v. 2961, 1472, 1237, 1094, 842, 800. HRMS (ESITOF) *m/z* (M-H)⁻ calcd for [C₁₇H₁₄F₃N₄OS]⁻ 379.0840; found 379.0881.

8. General procedure 5 (GP5)- Synthesis of sulfoximines

To a solution of N-cumyl sulfonylimidoyl fluoride (0.2 mmol, 1.0 equiv., 0.2 M), organometallic compound (0.2 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 6 h at the indicated temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into water (15 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (3 x 15 mL). The organic layers were collected, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtered, and the solvent was evaporated at reduced pressure. The compounds were purified by column chromatography as indicated for each entry, to afford the desired sulfoximine.

NB. Attempt to deprotect sulfoximine **7a** under hydrogenolytic conditions, employing an H-Cube® Pro microfluidic system equipped with a 10% Pd/C cartridge (15 bar H₂ pressure, 40 °C, **7a** 0.02 M in MeOH/AcOEt 1:1, 0.500 µL/min) failed.

N-cumyl-S-2-thienyl-S-methyl sulfoximine (**7a**)

Compound **7a** was prepared following **GP5** (diethyl ether, 0 °C) with MeMgBr and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 8:2, 28 mg, 50%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.58 – 7.54 (m, 2H), 7.44 (dd, *J* = 3.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.32 – 7.25 (m, 2H), 7.20 – 7.14 (m, 1H), 7.01 (dd, *J* = 5.0, 3.7 Hz, 1H), 3.15 (s, 3H), 1.68 (s, 3H), 1.58 (s, 3H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 150.2, 147.0, 132.4, 132.1, 128.0, 127.8, 126.2, 125.6, 59.9, 50.2, 33.4, 32.1. IR (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 2972, 1402, 1243, 1177, 1117, 1001, 852, 757, 697. HRMS (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₁₄H₁₇NNaOS]⁺ 302.0644; found 302.0642.

N-cumyl-S-hexyl-S-butyl sulfoximine (**7b**)

Compound **7b** was prepared following **GP5** (diethyl ether, -78 °C) with n-butyllithium and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 8:2, 10 mg, 15%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.61 – 7.56 (m, 2H), 7.32 – 7.26 (m, 2H), 7.23 – 7.16 (m, 1H), 2.86 – 2.76 (m, 2H), 2.73 – 2.59 (m, 2H), 1.75 – 1.55 (m, 10H), 1.37 – 1.19 (m, 10H), 0.91 – 0.84 (m, 6H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 150.6, 128.1, 126.3, 125.8,

58.6, 55.0, 54.7, 33.4, 31.5, 28.4, 25.6, 23.6, 22.5, 21.9, 14.1, 13.8. **IR** (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 2927, 2872, 1465, 1240, 1111, 763, 699. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z ($M+\text{Na}$)⁺ calcd for $[\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{33}\text{NNaOS}]^+$ 346.2175; found 346.2171.

N-cumyl-S,S-diphenyl sulfoximine (7c)

Compound **7c** was prepared following **GP5** with phenyllithium (diethyl ether, $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 8:2, 8 mg, 12%). **^1H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.95 – 7.89 (m, 4H), 7.66 – 7.59 (m, 2H), 7.47 – 7.20 (m, 8H), 7.21 – 7.12 (m, 1H), 1.63 (s, 6H). **$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 150.9, 145.0, 131.7, 128.9, 128.1, 128.0, 126.0, 125.6, 59.6, 33.3. **IR** (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3059, 2923, 1491, 1445, 1265, 1181, 1089, 757, 725. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z ($M+\text{Na}$)⁺ calcd for $[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{NNaOS}]^+$ 358.1242; found 358.1188.

9. General procedure 6 (GP6)- Synthesis of sulfonimidates

To a solution of sulfonimidoyl fluoride (0.1 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in corresponding alcohol (0.2 M), NaH (0.4 mmol, 16 mg, 4 equiv.) was added and the mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into water (15 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (3 x 15 mL). The organic layers were collected, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtered, and the solvent was evaporated at reduced pressure. The compounds were purified by column chromatography as indicated for each entry, to afford the desired sulfonimidate.

Isopropyl N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidate (8a)

Compound **8a** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 31 mg, 71%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.05 – 8.03 (m, 2H), 7.55 – 7.47 (m, 9H), 7.32 – 7.18 (m overlapping CDCl_3 9H), 4.23 (hept, $J = 6.3$ Hz, 1H), 0.79 (d, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 3H), 0.72 (d, $J = 6.3$ Hz, 3H) $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.9, 142.4, 132.0, 129.3, 128.8, 127.5, 127.3, 126.5, 75.1, 72.9, 22.5, 22.1 IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3057, 2924, 1445, 1299, 1191, 748, 700. HRMS (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$ calcd for $[\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{27}\text{NNaO}_2\text{S}]^+$ 464.1660; found 464.1659.

Ethyl N-tritylbenzenesulfonimidate (8b)

Compound **8b** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 27 mg, 63%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.09 – 8.07 (m, 2H), 7.58 – 7.50 (m, 9H), 7.30 – 7.20 (m overlapping CDCl_3 , 9H), 3.46 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), 0.76 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 3H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.7, 140.7, 132.3, 129.2, 129.0, 127.6, 127.5, 126.7, 72.7, 65.4, 14.2 IR (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3059, 2924, 1445, 1290, 1192, 749, 701. HRMS (ESITOF) m/z ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$ calcd for $[\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{25}\text{NNaO}_2\text{S}]^+$ 450.1504; found 450.1502.

Isopropyl N-tritylbutane-1-sulfonimidate (8c)

Compound **8c** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 23 mg, 55%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.49 – 7.47 (m, 6H), 7.30 – 7.18 (m, 9H), 4.29 – 4.25 (m, 1H), 3.04 – 2.96 (m, 2H), 2.04 – 1.95 (m, 2H), 1.49 – 1.44 (m, 2H), 1.10 – 1.09 (m, 3H), 1.00 – 0.96 (m, 3H), 0.93 – 0.88 (m, 3H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.0, 129.2, 127.4, 126.4, 74.6, 72.0, 56.2, 26.8, 22.9, 22.7, 21.6, 13.8. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3056, 2872, 1446, 1311, 1175, 844, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₆H₃₁NNaO₂S]⁺ 444.1973; found 444.1973.

Ethyl 2-phenyl-N-tritylethane-1-sulfonimidate (8d)

Compound **8d** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 24 mg, 53%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.50 – 7.48 (m, 5H), 7.34 – 7.18 (m, 15H), 3.60 – 3.51 (m, 2H), 3.49 – 3.23 (m, 4H), 0.90 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 147.7, 138.3, 129.1, 128.9, 128.6, 127.5, 126.9, 126.5, 72.1, 65.5, 55.9, 30.7, 29.8, 14.7. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) ν 3057, 2923, 1446, 1308, 1179, 747, 699. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₉H₂₉NNaO₂S]⁺ 478.1817; found 478.1810.

Isopropyl N-tritylpropane-2-sulfonimidate (8e)

Compound **8e** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 29 mg, 71%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.46 – 7.44 (m, 5H), 7.26 – 7.22 (m, 7H), 7.21 – 7.16 (m, 3H), 4.17 (hept, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 1H), 3.03 (hept, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 1.54 (d, *J* = 4.14 Hz, 3H), 1.53 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz, 3H), 1.12 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 3H), 0.82 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.2, 129.4,

127.4, 126.4, 74.7, 71.5, 56.9, 23.0, 22.7, 18.6, 17.6. **IR** (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3056, 2926, 1446, 1182, 1097, 845, 751, 700. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z ($M+\text{Na}$)⁺ calcd for $[\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{29}\text{NNaO}_2\text{S}]^+$ 430.1817; found 430.1800.

Ethyl 2-ethoxy-N-tritylethane-1-sulfonimidate (**8f**)

Compound **8f** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 17 mg, 40%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.47 – 7.44 (m, 6H), 7.30 – 7.18 (m, 9H), 3.97 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 3.62 – 3.53 (m, 4H), 3.46 – 3.37 (m, 2H), 1.23 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H), 0.90 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 3H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.6, 129.0, 127.4, 126.4, 72.3, 66.7, 65.6, 65.0, 54.4, 29.7, 15.1, 14.5 **IR** (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3056, 2924, 1489, 1314, 1197, 754, 701. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z ($M+\text{Na}$)⁺ calcd for $[\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{29}\text{NNaO}_3\text{S}]^+$ 446.1766; found 446.1749.

Ethyl 1-ethoxy-N-tritylpropane-2-sulfonimidate (**8g**)

Compound **8g** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (inseparable mixture of diastereomers, dr: 1:1, Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 11 mg, 25%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.46 – 7.42 (m, 6H), 7.28 – 7.16 (m, 9H), 4.12 – 4.04 (m, 1H), 3.85 – 3.78 (m, 1H), 3.77 – 3.25 (m, 5H), 1.62 – 1.56 (m, 3H), 1.29 – 1.16 (m, 3H), 0.90 – 0.86 (m, 3H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.9, 129.2, 127.5, 126.5, 71.8, 70.8, 70.3, 66.9, 65.9, 60.1, 59.6, 31.9, 29.9, 15.3, 14.7, 14.1, 13.2. **IR** (ATR, cm^{-1}) ν 3057, 2924, 1446, 1313, 1177, 753, 701. **HRMS** (ESITOF) m/z ($M+\text{Na}$)⁺ calcd for $[\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{31}\text{NNaO}_3\text{S}]^+$ 460.1922; found 460.1930.

Ethyl N-(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)benzenesulfonimidate (**8h**)

Compound **8h** was prepared following **GP6** and was obtained as a colourless oil after column chromatography on silica gel (Hex:AcOEt 9:1, 9 mg, 30%). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.05 – 7.99 (m, 2H), 7.67 – 7.60 (m, 2H), 7.58 – 7.46 (m, 3H), 7.37 – 7.31 (m, 2H), 7.24 – 7.16 (m, 1H), 3.84 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H), 1.85 (s, 3H), 1.81 (s, 3H), 1.13 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) 150.4, 140.2, 132.3, 128.8, 128.1, 127.6, 126.2, 125.3, 65.4, 60.2, 33.4, 32.6, 14.8. **IR** (ATR, cm⁻¹) 2977, 1445, 1298, 1195, 1007, 888, 742, 680. **HRMS** (ESITOF) *m/z* (M+Na)⁺ calcd for [C₂₆H₃₁NNaO₃S]⁺ 326.1293; found 326.1187.

10. Treatment of N-tritylsulfonimidoyl fluoride 2a with organometallics

11. Preparation of sulfonimidamide 5a – ¹⁹F NMR monitoring

N-trityl sulfinylamine **1a** (50 mg, 0.16 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in dry THF. LiHMDS (1.0 M in THF, 1.0 equiv., 160 μ L) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 5 minutes at room temperature. Subsequently, the solution was cooled to 0 $^{\circ}$ C and phenyllithium (0.16 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added dropwise, and the mixture was stirred at 0 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 minute. NFSI (0.36 mmol, 114 mg, 1.1 equiv.) was added in one portion and the first ^1H and ^{19}F NMR were recorded after 15 minutes (**event 1**). Subsequently, NaOH was added, and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature (**event 2**). Water (50 μ L) was added, and the mixture was stirred for additional 2 h at room temperature (**event 3**). The ^1H NMR spectrum of the reaction crude is reported.

12. Copies of NMR spectra (^1H , ^{13}C , ^{19}F)

13. References

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